

Location

Teknikhöjden, Stockholm - Sweden

Innovation

1.4 BIM for circular value flow planning

Partners

Ragn-Sells
Akademiska Hus
DEMO Consultants
TU-Berlin

SUMMARY OF SCOPE AND GOALS

This demonstration focuses on different inventory methods for identifying flat glass recycling and finding a method for transferring information between different software/programs and actors. This to secure that flat glass from existing buildings is recovered, processed, and used to produce new flat glass, ultimately reinstalled as a window component. The aim is to show how the inventory with a structured methodology and dataset enable the physical movement of components and the flow of information for enabling circular material flows.

The demonstration also shows how Circular Value Flow Planning (CVFP), along with the required digital capabilities, is integrated into the CP-IM platform. This includes using data for circularity assessments and strategic material planning

DATA TYPES, TOOLS, REPOSITORIES, URLS

Data types

Excel templates
2D drawings (pdf)
3D BIM models (rvt.)

Tools

iPad, laptops
Navis VLX scanner (mobile)
Matterport PRO3 (terrestrial scanner)
Revit (3D modeling software)

Communication

HTTP/WebSocket via Wi-Fi and Bluetooth.

IMPACT

LOW

Techno-Economic Impact

HIGH

Societal Impact

HIGH

Scientific Impact

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

- An inventory together with a 3D scanning is a more efficient way of making inventories of the built environment and gives higher accuracy.
If there is no BIM model and that needs to be created. It might be more efficient (in terms of calendar time) to just do a manual inventory. However, just a manual inventory will make it difficult to share the information in a value-creating way with multiple actors
- It is more time efficient to do an inventory using CP-IM compared to a manual inventory.
1 floor plan took 20 min and all of the building at Teknikhögden took 4h.
- A scanning can facilitate all relevant geometries and information to create a BIM model based on the scanning.
Yes, assuming that there are no hidden parts in the building that are to be part of the BIM model. Different scanning methods give different data granularity
- Can the data points collected in the inventory be shared in a scalable way using the CP-IM platform?
Yes, it is possible to share data points through the CP-IM platform.

CONTACTS

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